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DÉCLARATION DE BERLIN

VERS UNE POLITIQUE DES DROGUES BASÉE SUR LA DÉFENSE DES DROITS HUMAINS

La guerre menée aujourd'hui contre les drogues s'est transformée en spirale destructrice. Les principes sur lesquels repose la prohibition ont montré que cette guerre est un échec total.

L'idée d'un monde sans drogues est une utopie et les politiques de réduction de l'offre et la demande basées sur la violence institutionnelle ont échoué face aux réalités de chaque continent et région.

Ces politiques ont produit des dispositifs antidémocratiques, répressifs et autoritaires, qui n'ont fait que renforcer le pouvoir et l'influence économique des groupes criminels. La guerre mondiale contre les drogues a provoqué des violations systématiques des droits humains, la corruption, la criminalisation et l'emprisonnement de masse de certaines populations, en même temps que les risques sociaux et sanitaires pour les usagers de drogues illicites ont augmenté.

La prohibition est une erreur de stratégie politique qui s'est transformée en une idéologie morbide. La guerre contre les drogues a atteint une violence sans précédent en Amérique centrale et en Asie du Sud-Est, menant à la terreur et à la mort. Pendant ce temps, les succès de la dépénalisation de la consommation des drogues et le développement de nouveaux paradigmes sur les usages scientifiques et thérapeutiques des stupéfiants dans d'autres parties du monde révèlent la nature très contestable de la prohibition. La société civile et de la communauté scientifique ont su renouveler les approches et ont édifié la réduction des risques, afin d'améliorer la qualité de vie de tous les usagers des drogues, en même temps que les usagers problématiques retrouvaient des services sociaux et de santé adaptés.

En conséquence, et compte tenu des millions de personnes victimes de la guerre menée contre les drogues, nous, les hommes et les femmes avec des visions du monde diverses, en tant que chrétiens, militants, libres penseurs, défenseurs des droits de l'homme et des droits des usagers de drogues, implorons les Nations Unies et sa Commission des stupéfiants, le Bureau des Nations Unies contre la drogue et le crime, l'Union européenne, l'OEA, la CICAD, la CELAC, les hommes et femmes politiques, les églises, les communautés et les organisations sociales à: Arrêter la politique de guerre contre les drogues.

Sur la base du «Processus de réconciliation pour la paix, la justice et la création», nous appelons les organisations religieuses, les communautés chrétiennes, les groupes laïcs, les organisations de la société civile, les organisations internationales et les organisations sociales à mettre fin à la guerre contre les drogues.

Nous demandons l'amélioration de la coopération judiciaire pour un ciblage réel et efficace des organisations terroristes, des groupes terroristes et du blanchiment d'argent et d'actifs.

La promotion et l'analyse des alternatives aux politiques fondées sur l'interdiction et la répression.

La mise en place des stratégies de prévention et d'éducation en matière de drogue fondées sur des principes de réduction des risques et le respect des droits humains.

L'engagement de la société civile dans le processus post-UNGASS.

Le financement des campagnes d'information sur les politiques internationales et locales en matière de drogues autour des stratégies pragmatiques de prévention et de réduction des risques fondées sur des données scientifiques argumentées, sans préjugés ni aprioris sur les usagers ou les substances elles-mêmes.

La reconnaissance du droit des usagers des drogues à décider librement de leurs choix de vie conformément au principe de l'autodétermination.

Nous, les institutions et personnes signataires de cette déclaration, nous engageons à promouvoir la réforme du modèle actuel de contrôle international des drogues, en prônant une approche pragmatique fondée sur la santé publique et les droits humains. Cette réforme doit chercher à remédier les effets néfastes des politiques existantes en matière de drogues, prévenir les consommations problématiques des drogues licites ou illicites et lutter contre les réseaux mafieux de grande échelle.

Unis dans la diversité et animés par le besoin de justice et d'empathie qui nous inspire à aller vers l'avant, nous déclarons que la guerre contre les drogues doit cesser!

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nous méritons tous

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